

Date:

This study aims to assess the factors influencing knowledge and safety practices among dry fish handlers in the southern coastal region of Bangladesh. The study is being conducted by the Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, Patuakhali Science and Technology University (PSTU).

All information provided by you will be **kept strictly confidential** and used only for research purposes. Your participation in this study is completely voluntary, and you have the right to withdraw at any time without any consequences.

Would you be interested in participating in this study? a) Yes b) No

Participant's Signature/Thumb

Interviewer Signature

Section 1: Socio-demographic and other information

Age (years)	<input type="checkbox"/> <= 40 y	<input type="checkbox"/> >40 y
Gender	<input type="checkbox"/> Male	<input type="checkbox"/> Female
Educational level	<input type="checkbox"/> Illiterate	<input type="checkbox"/> Primary <input type="checkbox"/> SSC <input type="checkbox"/> HSC or above
Pattern of occupation	<input type="checkbox"/> Primary	<input type="checkbox"/> Secondary
Monthly income (BDT)	<input type="checkbox"/> <=20000	<input type="checkbox"/> 20001-40000 <input type="checkbox"/> >40000
Marital status	<input type="checkbox"/> Single	<input type="checkbox"/> Married
Type of employment	<input type="checkbox"/> Single	<input type="checkbox"/> Married
Toilet facilities		
Business ownership	<input type="checkbox"/> Single	<input type="checkbox"/> Joint
Involvement of paid workers	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Type of contract with workers	<input type="checkbox"/> Daily	<input type="checkbox"/> Monthly
Occupation during the off-season of dry fish	<input type="checkbox"/> Involving other occupations <input type="checkbox"/> Nothing	
Received training on dry fish handling and food safety	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Received training on waste management	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Experience of work (years)	<input type="checkbox"/> < 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 5 <input type="checkbox"/> >5
History of chronic diseases	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Suffered from any occupational health risk in the last three months	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No

Section_2: Personal hygiene knowledge

Statements	Yes	No	Neutra l
K1. Washing hands with soap before and after eating can prevent disease			
K2. Washing hands with soap after going to the toilet can prevent disease			
K3. Hand washing with soap after processing raw fish is mandatory			
K4. Using sanitary toilets improves food safety in addition to improving sanitary conditions			
K5. Using hand gloves and masks will reduce the risk of food contamination			
K6. Use of DDT (white powder) is hazardous to health			
K7. There are ten steps to hand washing tips for fish handlers.			
K8. If you are suffering from diarrhoea, cough, vomiting and fever, you should not catch fish			
K9. Hand sanitizer is not a complete substitute for hand washing			
K10. Wash your hands after sneezing or coughing			
K11. Clothes, aprons and head ware should be washed with soap and clean water regularly.			
K12. Jewelry, rings, nail polishes cannot be used while fishing			
K13. Bath should be taken every day after work			
K14. To prevent germs from getting stuck in the nails, the nails should be trimmed regularly			
K15. Food safety training should be attended at least once a year by the Fish processor.			
K16. Fish processor must require health checkup twice a year, even if they are not sick.			
K17. Hepatitis A, typhoid, cholera can be transmitted through contaminated food and water			
K18. Diseases caused by norovirus can be transmitted through contaminated food and water			

Section_3: Environmental hygiene knowledge

Statements	Yes	No	Neutra l
EK_1_ There should have drains facilities for sewage disposal in fish processing area.			
EK_2_ The fish processing area should be away from latrine or dumping sites			
EK_3_ There should have cold rooms and cold storage facilities in fish processing area			
EK_4_ Disinfection of workplaces regularly is necessary.			
EK_5_ Sources of clean water for hand washing and fish processing are required			

EK_6_Public toilets or good sanitation should be provided			
EK_7_A sanitary dustbin with a well-fitting lid is required in the workplace			
EK_8_The dustbin should be kept 4 inches or 10 cm above the ground to keep out rats and flies.			
EK_9_Keeping dried fish in damp places can lead to fungal/bacterial attack			
EK_10_Keeping dry fish in damp places can cause Aflatoxin			
EK_11_insect nets should be used on store room windows and doors to keep out flies.			
EK_12_Broken walls, walls and cracks need to be repaired to keep rats out of the store room.			
EK_13_Dustbins should be washed regularly with soap and disinfectant			
EK_14_Regular drainage should be done and the area should be cleared of dirt, excessive weeds should be cut			
EK_15_Excessive weeds around the processing should be cut			
EK_16_Dried fish should be stored on shelves, pallets, trays, trolleys or baskets			
EK_17_Adequate area and equipment are required for storage			
EK_18_Rotten fish, fish waste and other household waste should be disposed of in an environmentally friendly manner.			
EK_19_When storing dry fish, the walls and ceiling of the room should be at least 6 inches from the ground			
EK_20_Food grade polythene should be used during storage			

Section 4: Food safety knowledge

Statements	Yes	No	Neutral
FS_PH_1_Personal hygiene can reduce foodborne illness			
FS_PH_2_Hand washing before and after fishing is important			
FS_PH_3_Rubbing hands on the face, hair and other areas of the nose while fishing increases the health risk			
FS_PH_4_Using protective gloves while fishing reduces the chance of food contamination			
FS_PH_5_Eating or distributing any food with unclean hand is harmful for health.			
FS_PH_6_When coughing or sneezing, it is necessary to take protective measures to cover your face			
FS_PH_7_Fish should refrain from working if the body shows signs of injury or disease			
FS_PH_8_It is important to take a shower after work every day			
FS_PulH_1_A clean environment is essential to prevent pollution			
FS_PulH_2_It is important to wash the fish separation areas daily with water and sanitizer			
FS_PulH_3_Is it necessary to wash the utensils with sanitizer and soap after processing the fish?			

FS_PulH_4_ It is important to wash the knife used for cutting wet fish with water or sanitizer before and after use		
FS_PulH_5_ Wet fish is injurious to health when exposed to dry fish		
FS_TPCC_1_ Ice and freezing help preserve fish longer		
FS_TPCC_2_ To maintain fish quality, a freezer should be kept below 40°C/4.5°C		
FS_TPCC_3_ Keeping dried fish in packets reduces the chance of spoilage		
FS_TPCC_4_ Lean fish keep longer/better than oily fish		
FS_TPCC_5_ Fish should be stored as fresh as possible		
FS_TPCC_6_ Freezing fish kills bad bacteria		
FS_TPCC_7_ Fish that have been thawed can be refrozen		
FS_TPCC_8_ Contaminated fish has a different color, texture, smell or taste than fresh fish		
FS_TPCC_9_ Improper fish preservation methods can pose a threat to the health of consumers		
FS_FoodBD_1_ Foodborne illnesses are more harmful to children, elderly people and pregnant women		
FS_FoodBD_2_ The temperature of the freezer should be checked regularly		
FS_FoodBD_3_ Food borne diseases affect your health and economy		
FS_FoodBD_4_ Hepatitis A virus is one of the foodborne disease pathogens		
FS_FoodBD_5_ Heavy metals in dried fish can cause disease		
FS_FoodBD_6_ Use of pesticides/white powder in fish preservation is harmful to human health		
FS_FoodBD_7_ Pesticides/white powder cause human cancer		
FS_FoodBD_8_ Insecticide/white powder should be treated with gauze		
FS_FoodBD_9_ Washing fish with contaminated water can cause disease		

Section_5: Food safety practices

Statements	Always	Sometimes	Never
P_01_ A first aid box is available at my workplace.			
P_02_ Proper ventilation is maintained at my workplace/home.			
P_03_ I use hygiene PPE (e.g., gloves, mask, apron) during work.			
P_04_ Proper solid waste management is practiced in my workplace.			
P_05_ Safe drinking water is available at my workplace.			
P_06_ Adequate toilet facilities are available at my workplace			
P_07_ Waste is cleaned regularly in my workplace.			

P_08_Sun drying is properly practiced for fish processing.			
P_09_Rotten fish is disposed of in a proper and designated place.			
P_10_Clean and safe water is used for fish/dried fish processing.			
P_11_Measures are taken to reduce the smell of dried or rotten fish.			
P_12_Rotten fish is separated from good quality fish.			
P_13_Sufficient water is available to wash fish before drying.			
P_14_Proper methods are maintained for collection, packaging, and transportation of dried fish.			
P_15_Chemicals are safely used or not used in dried fish processing.			